

Synthesis of Substituted 1*H*-Sulphonylpyrazoles and 1*H*-Sulphonyl-2-pyrazolines and their Antibacterial Activities

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Substituted sulphonylpyrazoles and pyrazolines are synthesised from 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-benzenesulphonylhydrazide)-1*H*-pyrazole (2). The sulphonylhydrazide (2) on reaction with either acetylacetone or ethyl acetoacetate gives the corresponding 1*H*-sulphonylpyrazoles (5, 6). 4-Arylazo-1-sulphonylpyrazoles (9, 10) are synthesised from 2 by reacting either with α -aryloxyacetylacetone or ethyl α -aryloxyacetoacetate. 2 is reacted with mesityl oxide, benzalacetone, benzalacetophenone or cinnamaldehyde to give the corresponding substituted sulphonyl-2-pyrazolines (11-14). The compounds (5, 6, 9-14) are tested for their antibacterial activity.

SOME of the pyrazole derivatives possess anticancerous properties¹. Bispypyrazoles² and pyrazoles³ with 3- and 5-methyl groups are found to possess various biological activities. Pyrazoles with sulphonamido moiety attached at different positions are found to be biologically active⁴⁻⁸. Hence it was thought to be of interest to extend our work on the synthesis of sulphonamido compounds and to evaluate their antibacterial and pharmacological properties. This communication describes the reaction of sulphonylhydrazide with various carbonyl compounds to give substituted pyrazoles and pyrazolines.

Reaction of 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4'-benzenesulphonylhydrazide)-1*H*-pyrazole⁹ (2) with acetylacetone gave the corresponding hydrazone (3). Similarly, treatment of 2 with ethylacetoacetate gave the hydrazone (4). These hydrazones (3, 4) undergo cyclisation to pyrazoles (5, 6) under acidic conditions, but not under neutral conditions. The pyrazoles (5, 6) were obtained directly on reaction of 2 either with acetylacetone or with ethyl acetoacetate when carried out in acetic acid⁹. The structure of 5 and 6 was elucidated on the basis of ir and pmr spectra. The cyclisation of hydrazone to pyrazole was evident from the disappearance of bands at 3 100-3 380 cm⁻¹ (NH).

Alternatively, the pyrazole (5) was synthesised by reacting 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4-benzenesulphonylchloride)-1*H*-pyrazole⁶ (1) with 3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazole⁶ in presence of an organic base such as pyridine triethylamine (Scheme 1). The pmr spectrum of 5 exhibited signals at δ 2.2-2.32 due to methyl groups at 3- and 5-positions, besides the multiplet due to aromatic protons.

The reaction of the sulphonylhydrazide (2) with α -aryloxyacetylacetone^{9,10} gave the corresponding hydrazones (7a-c). Similar treatment of 2 with α -aryloxyacetoacetate^{10,11} gave the corresponding hydrazones (8a-c). These hydrazones (7a-c,

Scheme 1

8a-c) on treatment with acid underwent cyclisation to the corresponding pyrazoles (9a-c, 10a-c). The reaction of 2 either with α -aryloxyacetylacetone or with ethyl α -aryloxyacetoacetate, when carried out in the presence of acetic acid, gave the directly cyclised pyrazoles (9a-c, 10a-c) (Scheme 2). Structures of compounds 9 and 10 were elucidated from ir and pmr spectra. The structure was evident from the presence of a band at 1 590-1 600 cm⁻¹ (N=N) and the absence of NH absorption band in the ir spectra. The pmr spectra exhibited signals of three proton intensity at δ 2.2-2.33 due to methyl groups at 3- and 5-positions.

The reactivity of sulphonyl hydrazide (2) was further checked towards α,β -unsaturated keto compounds. In all the cases, the substituted pyrazolines¹² were obtained. Accordingly, the

sulphonylhydrazide (2) was reacted with various α,β -unsaturated keto compounds, viz. misityl oxide, benzalacetone, benzalacetophenone and cinnamaldehyde to give the corresponding substituted 2-pyrazolines (11-14) (Scheme 3), whose structures

were elucidated by ir and pmr spectra. The ir spectra showed band at 1 150 cm⁻¹ (SO₂) and disappearance of the band due to NH. The structure was further substantiated by pmr spectra which exhibited a triplet of a single proton at δ 5.12 (C₅-H) and a signal at δ 3.31 (C₄-H).

Biological activity: Compounds 5, 6, 9-14 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Saccharomyces*

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3-6, 11-14)*

Compd. no.	R	X	Z	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3	Me			258-9	78	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S
4	OEt			205	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S
5	Me			237-8	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S
6	OH			212	38	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
11	Me	Me	Me	131-2	37	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
12	Me	Ph	H	153	30	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S
13	Ph	Ph	H	180-4	35	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S
14	H	Ph	H	126-7	27	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S

*Elemental analyses of C, H, N and S were found to be satisfactory.

cerevisiae and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 2 mg ml⁻¹ and 5 mg ml⁻¹ in the nutrient agar media following the Ditch-plate method¹³. Compound 5 inhibited the growth of *S. typhi* and *E. coli*, 6 inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*, 11 inhibited the growth of *S. typhi*, 12 inhibited the growth of *B. subtilis*, while 14 inhibited the growth of *E. coli*. The rest of the compounds were not significantly active against the above bacteria.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (7a-10c)*

Compd. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
R = Me				
7a	Ph	187-8	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S
7b	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	254	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S
7c	2,4,6-Br ₃ C ₆ H ₂	212	63	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ Br ₃ N ₄ O ₂ S
R = OEt				
8a	Ph	157	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
8b	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	223	68	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₆ S
8c	2,4,6-Br ₃ C ₆ H ₂	184-5	63	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ Br ₃ N ₄ O ₄ S
R = Me				
9a	Ph	173	48	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
9b	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	207-8	40	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ S
9c	2,4,6-Br ₃ C ₆ H ₂	181	45	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Br ₃ N ₄ O ₂ S
R = OH				
10a	Ph	159	42	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S
10b	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	218-9	35	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₅ S
10c	2,4,6-Br ₃ C ₆ H ₂	176	38	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ Br ₃ N ₄ O ₃ S

*Elemental analyses of C, H, N and S were found to be satisfactory.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer, downfield from TMS as an internal reference.

Substituted hydrazones (3, 4): To a solution of sulphonylhydrazide² (2; 0.005 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added acetylacetone or ethyl acetoacetate (0.005 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 15 min. On cooling, a solid separated out which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol; ν_{max} 3 1170 (SO₂NH), 3 180 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 665 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

3,5-Dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl 4-(3', 5'-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl sulphone (5, 6). Method A: A solution of the hydrazones (3, 4; 0.005 mol) in AcOH (25 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured over ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-chloroform.

Method B: To a solution of sulphonylhydrazide (2; 0.003 mol) in AcOH (15 ml) was added acetylacetone or ethyl acetoacetate (0.003 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 15 h. The

cooled reaction mixture was poured over ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-chloroform (35-40%).

3,5-Dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl 4-(3',5'-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl sulphone (5): To a solution of 3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole⁸ (0.002 mol) and pyridine or triethylamine (0.5 ml) in DMF (20 ml), was added 3,5-dimethyl-1-(4'-benzenesulphonylchloride)-1H-pyrazole⁵ (1) (0.002 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 40 h. It was then cooled and poured over ice-water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-chloroform (15%); ν_{\max} 1 150 (SO₂), 1 605 and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.3-2.43 (12H, ss, 4 × CH₃) and 6.7-7.95 (6H, m, ArH and protons at C-4).

Hydrazones (7a-c, 8a-c): To a solution of sulphonylhydrazide (2; 0.005 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added α -arylozoacetylacetone or ethyl α -arylozoacetoacetate (0.005 mol) in DMF (10 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. On cooling, the resulting solid was washed with cold aqueous ethanol and crystallised from ethanol-DMF; ν_{\max} 7a 1 175 (SO₂NH), 3 160 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 660 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

3,5-Disubstituted-4-arylozo-1H-pyrazol-1-yl 4-(3',5'-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl sulphone (9a-c, 10a-c). *Method A:* The hydrazone (7, 8; 0.001 mol) taken into AcOH (20 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

Method B: A solution of sulphonylhydrazide (2; 0.002 mol) and α -arylozoacetylacetone or ethyl α -arylozoacetoacetate (0.002 mol) in AcOH (25 ml) was refluxed for 15 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (30-40%); ν_{\max} 9a 1 155 (SO₂), 1 610, 1 620 (C=N) and 1 590 cm⁻¹ (N=N); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.25-2.32 (12H, ss, 4 × CH₃) and 6.7-7.8 (10H, m, ArH, C₄-H).

3-Substituted-1H-2-pyrazolin-1-yl 4-(3',5'-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)phenyl sulphone (11-14). *General procedure:* A mixture of the sulphonylhydrazide (2; 0.002 mol) and α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compound (0.0021 mol) in AcOH (20 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured

into ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with water and subjected to column chromatography over neutral alumina using ethyl acetate-chloroform (1:3) as an eluant and further crystallised from ethyl acetate-ethanol; ν_{\max} 11 1 150 (SO₂), 1 610 and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.15-2.25 (9H, ss, 3 × CH₃), 1.45 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 3.25 (2H, s, C₄-H) and 6.7-7.8 (5H, m, ArH and protons at C-4); 13 1 150 (SO₂), 1 610 and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.2-2.25 (6H, ss, 2 × CH₃), 5.12 (1H, t, C₅-H), 3.31 (2H, d, J 8Hz, C₄-H) and 6.7-7.8 (15H, m, ArH and protons at C-4).

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References

1. C. W. NORLI and O. C. CHENG, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 545; W. WILSON and N. BOTTIGLIERI, *Cancer Chemotherapy*, 1962, **21**, 137.
2. G. T. DIFARSIA, C. SUAREZ and M. J. VITOLE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1981, **24**, 117.
3. J. B. WRIGHT, W. E. DULIN and J. H. MARKILLIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 102; R. E. ORTH, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, **57**, 537; G. A. BISTOCHI, A. RICCI and P. JACQUIGNON, *Farmaco. Ed. Sci.*, 1981, **36**, 315; V. J. BAUER, H. P. DULALIAN, W. J. FANSHAW, S. R. SAÏR, E. C. TOCUS and C. R. BOSHART, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 981.
4. G. S. SAHARIA and H. R. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 351.
5. P. S. FERNANDES, J. G. COUTINHO, K. B. COELHO and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 498.
6. P. S. FERNANDES, D. DESAI, N. GAWRI, S. PANDEY and H. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 818.
7. J. ELGUERO and G. COISPREAU, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1970, 2717; A. N. VOLKOV and A. N. NIKOLSKAYA, *Russ. Chem. Rev. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1977, **46**, 374.
8. K. VON AUWERS and E. CAUER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1930, **126**, 146.
9. W. U. MALIK, H. G. GARG and V. ARORA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 667; H. C. YAO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 2969.
10. S. M. PARMERTER, *Org. React.*, 1959, **10**, 11.
11. F. D. CHATTAWAY and R. J. LYR, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1938, **137**, 489; F. D. CHATTAWAY and D. R. ASHWORTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 475.
12. L. C. BEHR, R. FUSCO and C. H. JARBOR, *Chem. Heterocycl. Compd.*, 1967, **22**, 1.
13. L. J. BRADSHAW, "Laboratory Microbiology", 3rd. ed., W. B. Saunders, Philadelphia, 1979.